

Strategies for leaching and agricultural use of saline lands under conditions of water shortage

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Abstract. An analysis of the authors' experimental data on land leaching from salinization was carried out. The regularity of specific water consumption for salt leaching is assessed depending on the degree of soil salinization and negative environmental factors when leaching the soil with a layer of water. It is shown that leaching at high rates reduces soil fertility indices (NPK). The results of studies of alternative innovative methods of soil desalination and agricultural use of lands subject to salinization are presented. Soil desalination technologies that ensure enhanced salt leaching and water savings are considered: leaching against the background of deep soil loosening and the use of a local preparation containing an organic acid. The data of experiments with microbiological preparations produced in Uzbekistan, adapted to soil salinization and ensuring crop yields, are presented.

1 Introduction

Soil salinization, which is widespread in 49% of the irrigated territory of Uzbekistan, is a factor reducing the productivity of land, leading to losses in agricultural crops. In the regions of Uzbekistan, where soil salinization is most widespread, irrigated lands are leached during the winter-spring period. For this purpose, volumes of water are allocated annually according to the limits of the Ministry of Water Resources of the Republic, amounting to 25% of the annual volume of water and more. Traditionally, seasonal measures to reduce soil salinization of irrigated lands are leaching with a layer of water along checks.

During the period of large-scale melioration during the development of new lands (Hungry, Jizzakh and Karshi steppes), the development works included capital leaching of saline lands with leaching at very high rates of up to 30 thousand m³/ha [1-3]. Subsequently, a phased development of the land was proposed: leaching at a rate of 10 thousand m³/ha, followed by sowing salt-tolerant crops for the period of land development. In modern conditions, many of the previously developed scientific recommendations cannot be practically applied. This primarily concerns: the use of large volumes of water for leaching lands for cotton. In the context of probable global and local water problems in the

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republic, a water conservation strategy has been outlined and is being implemented in all areas of activity, and especially in the agricultural sector. The need to search for various, including new, low-water-intensive methods of combating soil salinization, to maintain the productivity of irrigated lands and ensure food security for the population, is an urgent task.

2 Environmental assessment of water-layer leaching technologies

According to the authors' experimental data, even with drainage, for leaching moderately saline soil, the specific water consumption is about 1000 m³/ha per 1 dS/m. When desalinating soils from 8 to 4 dS/m, the water consumption per 1 ha will be 4000 m³/ha. From the figures given, it follows that leaching saline lands with filling the checks with a layer of water is a water-consuming activity.

In addition, this technology has limited application: on lands not provided with drainage or flooded from the outside, as well as in conditions of low-permeability soils (including those with layers of gypsum and carbonates) and in some other cases.

There are a number of requirements for successful soil leaching from salts with a layer of water along checks, the absence of which is a limitation.

Limitations in the use of leaching along checks:

- Low soil permeability - water infiltration into the soil, including due to the presence of low-permeability dense layers (gypsum, carbonates).
- Close occurrence of groundwater.
- Lack of drainage of leaching water: drainage failure, backwater close to the surface of groundwater. Flooding of territories: creation of backwater of groundwater due to inflow from outside the territory of fields or the presence of general or local pressure of groundwater.
- Quite high labor and financial costs for soil preparation and leaching (taking into account updated data on prices for fuel and diesel and wages for tractor drivers and workers for 2024, they are ≈100 \$ / ha).
- High irrigation water inputs. At least 4000 m³/ha of water is needed: 2000 m³/ha, - to fill the free capacity of the aeration zone (salt dissolution) and 2000 m³/ha, - to displace salts into the drainage. According to experimental data, 2000 m³/ha desalinates the soil by chlorine ion: in the 0-30 cm layer by 35.5% and in the 0-70 cm layer by 24.2%, and according to ECe in the 0-70 cm layer, the soil desalinated by only 28%.

The efficiency of leaching is illustrated in Figure 1, constructed on the basis of experimental data from the Laboratory of Soil Research and Land Reclamation Processes of the Research Institute of Irrigation and Water Problems (NIIWP).

It is evident from Figure 1 that even with almost equal water supply to furrows (G. Gulyama, Syrdarya region, groundwater level = 2.2 m) and checks (Experimental farm, Khorezm region, dammed groundwater, groundwater level less than 1 m), the capacity for filling with water and ensuring water drainage play a crucial role. Figure 2, constructed based on experimental data, shows that even with good drainage of the site and effective leaching, at a groundwater depth of 2.5 m, soil salinization in the layer (0-30 cm), due to moisture evaporation, is restored by (60-90%) by the beginning of the cotton growing season.

Fig. 1. The effectiveness of saline soil leaching under different conditions.

Fig. 2. Illustration of the effectiveness of soil leaching by cells (in February-March) and salinity restoration in June.

Fig. 3. Influence of initial soil salinity on specific water consumption according to experimental data leaching by checks.

Based on the laws of salt leaching from the soil, it has been experimentally established that the salt release of the same soils (and the specific water consumption per unit of reduction in salinity) largely depend on the initial degree of soil salinity (Figure 3). According to the authors' experimental data, when leaching along checks, the specific water consumption per unit of salt leaching increases as the initial soil salinity decreases.

Experiments on leaching homogeneous light- and medium-loamy soils in mechanical composition in the Syrdarya region of Uzbekistan established the specific water consumption to reduce soil salinity by 1dS/m. They are: 480-500 m³/ha per 1 dS/m, - for a

strong degree of soil salinity (> 16 dS/m); 800-1000 m³/ha per 1 dS/m, - with an average degree of salinity (8 dS/m) and 2000-2500 m³/ha per 1 dS/m, - with an initially low degree of salinity (4 dS/m).

The above figures show that it is not rational to carry out leaching of slightly saline soils along checks: it is wasteful in terms of water and labor costs.

In addition to the above limitations of the application of the leaching technology along checks, due to natural and economic conditions, there are environmental aspects of the negative impact of leaching with a layer of water on soils.

Removal of nutrients during soil leaching (tables 1 and 2), which on the one hand reduces soil fertility, and on the other hand, pollutes underground (groundwater) waters that, in some cases, are used for drinking purposes.

Deterioration of water-physical properties due to dispersion (and swelling) of soil particles and compaction of the soil after leaching which is illustrated in Figure 4. The effect of leaching with large amounts of water, on the restoration of initial density and low filtration capacity of loosened soils is described in the source [4].

Fig. 4. Illustration of soil compaction after leaching.

Table 1. Changes in the content of salts, humus and nutrients during cotton irrigation and leaching (Experiment in vegetation vessels with the biopreparation RIZOKOM-1, 0-5 cm).

Observation period	ECe dS/m		Humus, %		P ₂ O ₅ , ppm		K ₂ O, ppm		
	Control	Test*	Control	Test	Control	Test	Control	Test	
Initial soil 05.06	10.4	10.4	1.86	1.86	86.4	86.4	725	725	
After irrigation - 01.08	24.8	27.2	1.62	1.87	90.4	79.3	863	915	
22.08, after leaching	11.0	8.3	1.04	1.18	68.2	65.1	701	458	
Change from irrigation: 05.05 to 01.08	Absolute value	14.4	16.8	-0.24	0.01	4	-7.1	138	190
	%	138	162	-13	1.0	5.0	-8	19	26
Change from soil leaching, 01.08 and 22.08	Absolute value	-13.8	-18.9	-0.58	-0.69	-22.2	-14.2	-162	-457
	%	-56	-69	-36	-37	-25	-18	-19	-50

*Test- option with the RIZOKOM-1.

Table 2. Changes in the content of nutrients during soil leaching in field conditions (2016, Mirzaabad district, Syrdarya region, Uzbekistan).

Observation period	Content in the layer 0-70 cm, ppm					
	N-NH ₄		P ₂ O ₅		K ₂ O	
	Control*	Test**	Control	Test *	Control*	Test *
Before leaching	30.9 (±8.2)	22.4 (±3.5)	15.6 (±7.9)	12.1 (±1.8)	439 (±91)	401 (±86)
After leaching	23.4 (±7.4)	24.0 (±3.5)	15.4 (±6.3)	17.5 (±6.3)	175 (±35)	141 (±25)
The difference: "before" - "after"	-7.4	1.6	-0.3	5.4	-264	-260
% to initial	-24	7	-2	45	-60	-65

*The relationship is significant according to the two-sample t-test with equal variances;

** Test,- option with the preparation Biosolvent.

Table 1 shows that leaching in vessels with a water supply rate of 1500 m³/ha, along with leaching of salts by 56-69%, also reduced the content of humus (36-37%), phosphorus (18-25%) and potassium (19-50%) to the original content. Field research data on leaching soil from salts with a water supply of 2000 m³/ha (Table 2) show a decrease in mobile nitrogen (24%) and potassium (60-65%).

3 Improving technologies for leaching saline soils

Methods of enhancing the leaching of salts by loosening the soil and using chemical ameliorants were studied in Uzbekistan in the 80s and 90s, during the mass leaching of saline lands during their development [5]

During the same period, the effect of deep loosening on the intensity of leaching of salts from loosened soil by precipitation was studied [6]. Research has also proven the effect of loosening the soil in early spring on reducing the accumulation of salts in the soil during irrigation of cotton and on the restoration of salinity by autumn [7].

Currently, harmless chemical preparations of the "Spersal" series, which are soil improvers and desalinizers, have been developed in the world based on polymaleic acid [8-9]. They enhance the leaching of salts and improve the soil structure by mobilizing soil calcium.

The authors studied the possibility of reducing water consumption for washing soil from salts by: improving their filtration properties by deep loosening and chemical action on the leaching of salts by treating the soil with a 10% solution of the Biosolvent preparation (pH = 1.9), a local analogue of the Spersal preparation.

The above measures were studied separately and together as a method of desalinating the soil using atmospheric precipitation. The results of the study showed the possibility of using sprinkling for washing soils, both during land restoration and during washing soils along furrows.

Research has proven the effectiveness of saline land reclamation technologies using loosening and Biosolvent, alternatives to soil leaching by checks and suitable for use in cases of water shortage: desalination of highly saline soil (from 16 dS/m to 5 dS/m) by precipitation and furrow leaching of moderately saline soil (leaching of up to 60% of harmful salts).

When studying soil leaching along furrows, it was found that changing the water-physical properties of the soil during loosening increases the leaching of salts by 1.6-1.8 times, and changing the chemical properties of the soil (using Biosolvent) - by 1.7-1.9 times. The combined effect of using loosening and Biosolvent increases the leaching of salts by 3.0 times in relation to the control. It was also found that loosening helps maintain soil moisture in the 30-70 cm horizon by 3-4% higher than in the control.

According to experimental data, the Biosolvent preparation allows increasing the efficiency of leaching along checks (up to 30-40%), and when used during the growing season of irrigation along furrows, it reduces soil salinity in the root zone of plants by 30% more effectively. As a result of managing the salt regime during the growing season, the resulting increases in cotton yield were no less than 25% (7.5 c/ha).

4 Application of biotechnology to maintain productivity of saline soils

In the world practice of salinity control and adaptation of agricultural production on saline soils, technologies alternative to water leaching of salts are being developed.

One of the ways to prevent crop damage from salinization is the use of biotechnology in growing crops on unfavorable, degraded and saline soils. Obviously, biotechnologies for increasing agricultural productivity of saline soils include: cultivation of more salt- and drought-tolerant plants, green fertilization, application of organic additives, use of various natural microorganisms that have a beneficial effect on plant nutrition and development under saline soil conditions.

A promising biotechnology that allows plants to survive and produce crops, even in saline soils, is the treatment (inoculation) of plant seeds with microbiological preparations and the creation of a favorable biological environment in the root zone (rhizosphere) due to the activity of microorganisms. "The use of salinity-tolerant rhizobacterial inoculates (PGPR) that stimulate plant growth may become a promising tool for combating salinity in agricultural fields, thereby increasing global food production. The beneficial effects of PGPR include enhancing key physiological processes, as well as water and nutrient uptake, photosynthesis, and source-sink communication, which promote plant growth and development" [10].

The beneficial effects of microbial seed inoculation technology include enhancing physiological processes in plants, as well as water and nutrient absorption, photosynthesis, which promote growth and development [11].

Publications [11-12] highlight the importance of PGPR application as a viable green alternative for improving crop production and sustainability. Plant growth promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) have become an alternative to the use of synthetic pesticides and fertilizers that have toxic effects on human health and the environment [12]. The author discusses the main mechanisms of direct action of PGPR on biological nitrogen fixation, availability of phosphorus, zinc and potassium to plants, as well as the production of phytohormones that stimulate plant growth.

Literary sources also describe the mechanism of the effect of seed inoculation on the nitrogen production by plants. As a result of the inoculant application, nodules are formed on the roots, which fix molecular nitrogen (N_2) from the air and convert it into a form accessible to plants (NH_4^+). Due to this unique process, the plant receives from the air the necessary amount of nitrogen for its growth and development "prolonged", throughout the entire vegetation period. This process allows to reduce the amount (or to refuse to introduce into the soil) of mineral nitrogen, without reducing the yield, since the plant becomes "self-sufficient" in this nutrient.

The Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan has developed new, environmentally friendly bacterial fertilizers and biopreparations to improve soil fertility, crop yields and the quality of agricultural products [13]. Bacterial fertilizers of complex action based on new local strains of phosphorus-mobilizing bacteria: 1) FOSSTIM-1 and FOSSTIM-3, respectively, for pre-sowing treatment of seeds of industrial and vegetable crops. Biopreparations of complex action based on new local strains of salt-tolerant phosphorus- and potassium-mobilizing rhizobacteria with polyfunctional properties: RIZOKOM -1, RIZOKOM -2, respectively, for pre-sowing treatment of cotton and wheat seeds grown on saline soils. A new bioagrotechnology has also been developed for growing crops on saline soils, based on the complex use of new generation bacterial fertilizers of the TERIA-S series, which includes beneficial salt-tolerant bacteria isolated from highly saline soils of the Kungrad district of the Republic of Karakalpakstan. According to the author of the development [13] these microorganisms have a complex of polyfunctional properties that are useful for soil and plants (they dissolve tricalcium phosphates, potassium aluminosilicates and gypsum in the soil; convert phosphorus, calcium, potassium, silicon, sulfur, nitrogen and other microelements into forms that are assimilable for plants; have antagonistic activity to the main phytopathogenic agricultural crops; withstand high concentrations of toxic salts in soils; are resistant to low and high soil temperatures; have phytohormonal and growth-

stimulating activity; accumulate heavy metals in soils; reduce the degree of phosphatization, salinity and pH of the soils).

The authors of this article field experiments conducted in the Syrdarya, Khorezm and Fergana regions of Uzbekistan established a significant increase in cotton and mung bean yields under the influence of above-mentioned domestic microbiological preparations RIZOKOM-1 and TERIA-S, which is confirmed by statistical processing of phenological observation data. Thus, in the Syrdarya region, despite the soil salinity in the 0-70 cm layer on cotton from 3.9 to 6.8 dS / m (average salinity), due to the use of the biopreparation RIZOKOM-1, increases in the cotton yield were obtained: from 5.5 to 14.6 c / ha. The increase in the yield of the legume crop mung, when treating seeds with the TERIA-S preparation in the Dangara district of the Fergana region, was 5.1 c / ha of grain, with soil salinity of 2.3 dS / m (Figure 5).

The study of the effect of microbiological preparations on soils and crop yields showed the following:

- The microbiological preparations RIZOKOM-1 and TERIA-S have a positive effect on the growth and development of plants and increase the yield of cotton and mung bean crops by 20 -30 % and more.
- During monitoring of soil salinity and fertility indicators by control points in the field, it was noted that there was no significant effect of RIZOKOM-1 biopreparation on them. This can be explained by both uneven fertilizer application and movement of salts (and fertilizer) across the field during irrigation. That is, microorganisms 'work' only in the root zone of plants, so to control the processes occurring in the soil, it is necessary to conduct observations in the rhizosphere of plants - a thin layer of soil adjacent to the roots.
- When using the TERIA-S product on crops of the legume crop mung bean (with a low degree of soil salinity), by the end of the growing season of the crop, an increase in the content of nutrients in the soil layer of 30-70 cm was noted: nitrate nitrogen - by 6%, phosphorus by 28% and potassium by 16%, to the original content.
- At application of RIZOKOM-1 preparation in vegetation vessels, an increase in water-holding capacity of soil was revealed: 2-2,5 % (during the period plant of cotton growth) and up to 6-7 % - after soil leaching.
- When leaching the soil in vegetation vessels, better soil leaching was found. From which it is logical to draw a preliminary conclusion about the improvement of aggregate and other properties (density state) under the influence of biopreparations.

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that microbiological preparations affect the conditions for plant development, creating a biological barrier to the influence of harmful environmental factors. Therefore, quantitative changes in soil salinity may not be noticed during the growing season, but plants can exhibit salt tolerance associated with the influence / protective role of microorganisms. From the analysis of published sources, it follows that the issue of the influence of this biotechnology on plants has not been fully studied, while its effect on soil properties is even less studied.

Fig. 5. Changes in soil salinity from the beginning to the end of the growing season and crop yield in experimental variants.

I Field experiment with the biopreparation RIZOKOM-1 during the vegetation of 2015, Mirzaabad, layer 0-70 cm; II The same, during the vegetation of 2016, Mirzaabad, layer 0-70 cm; III Experiment in vegetation vessels with the biopreparation RIZOKOM-1, layer 0-5 cm sowing cotton and washing; IV Field experiment crop-mung bean, Fergana, 2023 biopreparation TERIA-S, layer 30-70 cm

5 Conclusion

In the conditions of the inevitability of the transition to the economical use of limited water resources, both for irrigation and for the reclamation of saline lands, the study of international approaches to the management of the salt regime of irrigated soils, in combination with the analysis of experimental data conducted in specific local conditions, using different soil desalination technologies, allows us to take a broader look at the problem.

It is necessary to reasonably select measures to maintain saline soils, based on their economic and resource capabilities. Also of the utmost importance is the availability of information on the degree of soil salinization and its physical properties (infiltration, bulk density, the presence of gypsum layers) in a particular field. Despite many of the latest achievements and preparations and technologies, water is the main resource and without it,

it is impossible to conduct agriculture in the arid zone, including reclamation work to reduce soil salinization.

To enhance the leaching of salts under the influence of gravitational water flows (precipitation, leaching water, vegetation irrigation), it is recommended to carry out deep loosening of the soil in advance (early autumn), and immediately before the water enters the field prepared for leaching, spray the soil surface with an environmentally safe 10% solution of ameliorant - Biosolvent.

Biotechnology, as the creation of a favorable environment in the root zone for the survival of plants under salt stress, seems promising to us and has a great future. It is advisable to continue in-depth research on testing locally produced microbiological preparations on various soils by genesis and degree of salinization, and on various crops, in order to establish criteria for the conditions of "operability" of bacteria in different conditions, including under conditions of soil moisture deficit (irrigation of crops) in the arid zone. So far, it is not possible to consider this a panacea; research is required. So far, flushing (reducing soil salinization with the help of and moving salts downward with the gravitational flow of water) is preferable, but it is possible to use all of the above experimentally proven measures in combination, or acting according to the situation, based on the conditions: "if", "if", "if".

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